

Improving OA Book Usage Data Quality and Assuring Reader Privacy and Ethical Data Use via Community Data Sharing Managed by an Industry Data Space (IDS)

Author: Christina Drummond, Executive Director, OA Book Usage Data Trust

Photo by [Joshua Sortino](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Contents

I.	Background: Open Access Usage Data Exchange for Digital Book Publishing, Discovery, and Analytics	2
1.	Current State	2
2.	Processing and Sharing of OA eBook Usage (OAEBU) Data	2
3.	Why the COUNTER Standard Doesn't Solve the Problem	3
4.	Use Cases for High-Quality, On-demand Usage Data	4
5.	The OA Book Usage Data Trust Effort	1
II.	Exploring an Industry Data Space (IDS) for OA Publishing	2
1.	Interacting with a Data Space: Data Providers, Data Consumers, and Data Intermediaries	1
	Interoperability enabled by a web of interconnected data intermediation services.....	1
2.	IDS Governance Building Blocks: Policy and Practices to Steward Global Sovereign Data Exchange	2
	Evolving data regulations and controls – moving from fully open to as controlled as necessary.....	2
	Security and risk management for IP Addresses (usage data) depends on geography.....	3
	Developing principles through community consultation	3
	IDS sustainability and balanced stakeholder-based governance	4
3.	IDS Technical Building Blocks: Scaffolding Data Quality, Trust, and Neutral Data Exchange.....	4
	Streamlining data curation, exchange, and aggregation.....	5
	Surfacing common goods that are otherwise not available	6
	Conclusion	6
	Bibliography.....	7
	Acknowledgements.....	7

I. Background: Open Access Usage Data Exchange for Digital Book Publishing, Discovery, and Analytics

The growth of public and open access (OA) publishing has resulted in digital book content being hosted on multiple systems around the globe. Book readers may access content via publisher websites, institutional repositories, book collection aggregators, and digital libraries. All such organizations generate usage data tied to books and their authors.

1. Current State

When combined, such cross-platform usage data can illuminate the reach and impact of a book, collection, or service. Book authors, publishers, libraries, and funders seek high-quality, holistic views of how their books are used, discovered, or accessed around the world: how often, by whom, and in what ways. (See Section 4) Yet, while each organization can access their own granular page-views and download data, viewing one’s organization’s information in a trusted, high-quality global context remains challenging.

Book publishing, distribution, and discovery stakeholders have long collected and reported on internal web analytics related to the views and downloads, i.e. “usage” of digital book content. This data can inform operations, marketing, print, investment, and strategy. Such web analytics, or “raw usage data” takes the form of IP addresses and time stamps related to specific readers and organizations, as well as machine-based access through mechanisms such as “bots”.

Yet, for evidence-based decision-making, context matters. To advance analytics related to the impacts of publicly accessible scholarship, scholarship usage data itself must become more FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

2. Processing and Sharing of OA eBook Usage (OAEBU) Data

Such OAEBU data creators have a duty of care when they share their usage data with others. They must: 1) make sure the data is interpreted appropriately, 2) ensure that the disclosure is compliant with privacy and data regulations, and 3) prevent sharing that could negatively impact operations. While some public organizations publish versions of their usage statistics in the open for others to scrape or harvest for products and services, others limit access to those with a proscribed business relationship and specific terms of use.

When an eBook is accessed via a reader or website, usage data is created tied to a specific IP-address. This information is processed and transferred downstream to be aggregated or visualized within structured reports and dashboards. Resulting graphics reflect the reach of a given book, author, or publisher. Yet, as usage data is handed off between organizations in the data supply chain, additional processing can occur complicating usage data interoperability. In the current diffuse system, individual libraries, publishers, Library Management Systems (LMS), and analytics services normalize, interpret, and aggregate usage to

Figure 1: Usage Capture and Reporting for OA Books. (Clarke and Ricci 2021b)

support reporting, visualizing and analytics.(Clarke and Ricci 2021a) In the US, library consortia are developing data lakes to facilitate sharing across their own members.¹ Emerging “data lake” efforts encourage partners to add their data into a shared, central lake for partners to pull from as needed.² While access to the ecosystem can be secured, such data pooling introduces risk thereby increasing the need for trust. While it may be easy to trust fellow members of a consortium, book discovery and publishing is global.

Global efforts index and provide a directory of OA books³, facilitate access to publicly accessible usage related to the European Open Science Cloud⁴, and assist institutional repositories with the conversion of raw usage data into industry standard COUNTER compliant reports⁵. Having evolved through five versions from 2003 to 2022, Release 5 of the COUNTER Code of Practice provides industry standards to facilitate consistency in usage reporting and, “enable[s] libraries to compare data received from different publishers and vendors.”⁶ Per COUNTER’s Release 5 Code of Practice, this provides, “a framework for the recording and exchange of online usage statistics for the major categories of e-resources (journals, databases, books, reference works, and multimedia databases) at an international level...cover(ing) the following areas: data elements to be measured, definitions of these data elements, content and format of usage reports, requirements for data processing, requirements for auditing, and guidelines to avoid duplicate counting.”⁷

3. Why the COUNTER Standard Doesn’t Solve the Problem

Despite COUNTER’s broad acceptance as a community standard, adoption is not universal. Smaller presses and individual publishers may face resource challenges in adopting COUNTER, instead relying on tools such as Google Analytics that further complicate usage data interoperability. This presents a challenge to data users, but one that may be ameliorated by encouraging such providers to use COUNTER’s freely-available formats (tabular and JSON) for data exchange even in the event they are unable to implement full COUNTER processing. Use of COUNTER’s SUSHI schema as a standard API for data collection would similarly reduce the impact of having to collect, standardize, aggregate, benchmark, and interpret usage data across varied sources including emailed reports, password-protected dashboard platforms, and machine-readable APIs.

While many hundreds of publisher platforms deliver audited, trusted usage metrics through COUNTER-compliant reports, aggregating usage metrics across platforms is not common. Commercial organizations in particular are often unable to provide their raw usage data to competitors due to dynamics that cannot be resolved by trust alone. In this environment, multiple challenges exist for those who share generated usage data with others (data creators), and for those who rely on such data to provide reporting or services analytics (data users).

¹ For example, the [Ivy Plus Libraries Confederation Platform for Open Discovery](#)

² For a primer on the relational data repositories known as data lakes and data warehouses, see: Nambiar A, Mundra D. An Overview of Data Warehouse and Data Lake in Modern Enterprise Data Management. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*. 2022; 6(4):132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc6040132>. For a description of how data spaces relate to data warehouses, see <https://dih.telekom.net/en/welcome-to-data-spaces-storage-is-secondary-it-director-interview-with-prof-chris-s-langdon/>

³ [Directory of Open Access Books \(DOAB\)](#)

⁴ For example, the [Usage Counts Service by OpenAIRE](#),

⁵ For example, the [Institutional Repository Usage Service \(IRUS\)](#)

⁶ COUNTER Website. <https://www.projectcounter.org/about/> Accessed on Feb 8, 2023.

⁷ COUNTER Code of Practice for Release 5 Scope. <https://www.projectcounter.org/code-of-practice-five-sections/introduction-to-counter-code-of-practice-release-5/>. Accessed on March 16, 2023.

4. Use Cases for High-Quality, On-demand Usage Data

Focus groups with libraries and publishers clarified that use cases for OA book usage reporting go beyond static impact metric reporting to authors, institutions and funders.⁸ Libraries and editors want access to high-quality, recent usage data to enable operational decision-making through linked big data. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Why organizations want to access usage data. Illustrated by the Use Cases for OA Book Usage Data. Eniola, Philemon, Drummond, Christina, & Hawkins, Kevin. (2022). OA eBook Usage Data Use-Cases by Stakeholder Diagram. Zenodo.

A shared infrastructure opportunity exists to improve and simplify the management, curation, aggregation, and benchmarking of multi-platform usage data. Benefits of the economies of scale generated by simplified data exchange go beyond operational efficiencies and cost savings. Shared infrastructure could provide broader societal impacts for the environment and innovation. Reduced duplicative data processing and storage could lead to ecosystem-wide energy use reductions. Should fewer resources at individual institutions be required for usage data harvesting, curation, and aggregation – such human capital could be redirected towards developing innovative, in-demand niche analytics for specific book stakeholders (editors, press administrators, sales and marketing, etc.). Identifying common processes and shared infrastructure opportunities is the first step toward achieving such benefits.

⁸ Drummond, Christina, & Hawkins, Kevin. (2022). OA eBook Usage Data Analytics and Reporting Use-cases by Stakeholder. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5889141>

5. The OA Book Usage Data Trust Effort

From 2017 to 2019, scholarly book publishing stakeholders came together through multiple funded efforts to explore the opportunities related to economies of scale in usage data reporting (Hawkins and O’Leary 2019; Watkinson 2017). From 2020 to 2022, a project team funded by the Mellon Foundation piloted the exchange of OA book usage data for proof of concept analytics dashboards for university presses, a commercial publisher, and digital library. Technical research and development resulted in a repository of Apache Airflow workflow automation code to automate usage data retrieval and processing from provided feeds from DOAB, Google Analytics, Google Books, IRUS-UK, OAPEN, ONIX, and UCL Discovery. Connector and data processing workflows related to mapping book products, linking metrics, and exporting results were

OA Book Usage Data Trust

Vision Community governed sharing of quality, interoperable, OA book usage data

Mission Champion strategies for the improved publication and management of open-access books by exchanging reliable usage data in a trusted, equitable, and community-governed way

Community Principles

Inclusive	Ethical	Data Exchange Focused	Responsive and Extensible
Sustainable	Transparent	Collaborative	Community Informed

2023 Board of Trustees
Charles Watkinson, UoM Publishing
Dimitris Pierrikos, OpenAIRE
Jennifer Kemp, Crossref
Jon Elwell, EBSCO/GOBI
Jo Lambert, JISC/IRUS
Lorraine Estelle, Information Power
Sharla Lair, LYRASIS (Board Chair)
Tasha Mellins-Cohen, Project COUNTER
Wendy Queen, Project MUSE
Christina Drummond, Executive Director

Governance Building Block Project Pls
Christina Drummond, OAEBUDT/UNT
Prodromos Tsiavos, OpenAIRE
Yannick Legré, OPERAS

Figure 3: OA Book Usage Data Trust Vision, Mission, and Principles as of March 2023

documented.⁹ In addition, an environmental scan of existing usage data related platforms and services and a legal review was conducted to explore legal issues related to the development of a data trust for multi-party usage data exchange. (Clarke 2021) (Gambill West 2021) These outputs, the usage data supply chain report and the stakeholder use-cases led the project team and Advisory Board to split the project into two distinct efforts with separate staffs and governance. The primary goal of the separation was to ensure the OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT)¹⁰ could neutrally facilitate cross-platform usage data exchange, aggregation, and benchmarking as core infrastructure, without allegiance or preference for a single usage data visualization or metrics service. Legally, this step was viewed as necessary to prepare for the enactment of the European Data Governance Act which “seeks to increase trust in data sharing, strengthen mechanisms to increase data availability and overcome technical obstacles to the reuse of data...(by) support(ing) the set-up and development of common European data spaces in strategic domains, involving both private and public players.” (“European Data Governance Act | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future” 2023). A Board of Trustees was elected for the OAEBUDT to provide community governance over the effort based on the mission, vision, and core principles developed by 2022. (Figure 3)

Team members reviewed literature on collaborative data governance mechanisms, noting the lessons learned from by other efforts. A survey of existing frameworks and principles for open scholarly infrastructure¹¹ informed the developing of the OAEBUDT mission, vision, and core principles¹². Research by the Open Data Institute on trust within data networks¹³ and data network sustainability¹⁴ prompted a global search for a technical infrastructure capable of providing usage data contributors with the assurances they need to exchange sensitive data in ways that are as openly transparent as possible

⁹ See https://oaebu-workflows.readthedocs.io/en/latest/oaebu_workflows/index.html#telescope-workflows

¹⁰ In 2022 the effort moved to rebrand as the OA Book Usage data trust, dropping electronic from “eBook”. Given broad awareness of the OAEBU acronym as a part of the project’s brand, the E remained in the acronym. Branding is expected to evolve as the effort launches a production IDS service.

¹¹ See Christina Drummond, Neylon, Cameron, Sherer, John, & Moore, Samuel. (2020). OA eBook Usage Data Trust: Related Principle Statements and Frameworks Ideation Output. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5842029>

¹² Kemp, Jennifer, Potter, Peter, Scrivener, Brian, Watkinson, Charles, & Skinner, Katherine. (2021). Guiding Principles for OA Book Usage Data Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5842414>

¹³ <https://theodi.org/article/designing-trustworthy-data-institutions-report/>

¹⁴ http://theodi.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/OPEN_Designing-sustainable-data-institutions_ODI_2020.pdf

and as controlled as necessary. The European Commission driven international data spaces / industry data spaces (IDS) frameworks¹⁵ and the zero-copy integration framework¹⁶ in Canada surfaced as ways to foster direct public-private data exchange through machine-readable semantic data governance at the metadata level. Such efforts allow data contributors to specify access and allowable processing for the data they share. This highly disruptive, zero-copy data space approach is distinct from the status quo where applications harvest or scrape open data for reuse. Driven by data ethics and maturing data governance practices, dynamic exchange focused models such as the IDS can provide more timely direct access to data from root sources.

As the IDS movement provides a community of emerging data spaces¹⁷, shared resources, technical specifications, and certification standards, it became a roadmap for the OAEBUDT, recognizing that infrastructure and agreements designed for OA book usage could be extensible to all open scholarship usage data exchange. In 2021, the OA Book Usage Data Trust effort aligned with the GAIA-X and Horizon Europe funded IDS frameworks, technical specifications, and open-source development community to rapidly apply their lessons learned for the good of OA book usage data exchange.

II. Exploring an Industry Data Space (IDS) for OA Publishing

Streamlining the legal and data governance required for interoperability and systems integration is at the heart of the rationale for a data space.

As companies increase data controls and limitations on data use in response to ethical concerns and regulatory compliance, there is a shared need to manage data exchange and processing through automated semantic data governance that facilitates dynamic data exchange flows, processing, and controlled use across public and commercial parties. Organizations will still require data warehouses and data lakes to internally gather, index, and query diverse data within their own organizations and secure networks; however, a data space can provide an industry-wide hub through such secure environments can interoperate for specific, rule-based data brokerage.

Through membership in the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), members of the OAEBUDT “Governance Building Blocks” project¹⁸ access and adapt lessons and infrastructure being developed by other industries. IDSA working groups, task forces, and developer communities are actively documenting technical ontologies, model contracts and rulebooks, and technical IDS infrastructure certification specifications. While interoperability across industry data spaces is core to the EU’s data strategy, each data space must be customized for a specific ecosystem, such as scholarly publishing, to meet the needs of those stakeholders. Hence, the OAEBUDT is serving as the vehicle by which scholarly book publishers are developing their data space participation terms and data sharing and use policies.

¹⁵ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/knowledge-base/design-principles-for-data-spaces>

¹⁶ <https://www.datacollaboration.org/zero-copy-integration>

¹⁷ The OA Book Usage Data Trust joined as a member of the [International Data Spaces Association](#) in 2022

¹⁸ Funded through the 2022-2025 Mellon Foundation award, “OAEBU Data Trust: Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks”

1. Interacting with a Data Space: Data Providers, Data Consumers, and Data Intermediaries

To provide or access data securely across platforms and countries, organizations can connect to a data space as data providers and/or data users i.e., data consumers in IDS parlance. According to the IDSA Data Rulebook and marketing materials¹⁹:

***Data Providers** grant access or share data for specific usage by data consumers. “They are not data subjects, within the specific data in question, but rather have legal authority to grant access to or share certain personal data or non-personal data”.*

***Data Consumers** have “lawful access to certain personal or non-personal data and the right, including under Regulation (EU) 2016/679 for personal data, to use that data”. In an IDS, they can search for and use data from different data providers according to the data usage policy.*

In an IDS for OAEBU data, creators of usage data act as **OAEBU Data Providers**. **OAEBU Data Consumer** organizations find and securely access usage data from multiple data providing platforms per data interoperability and reuse policies set forth by the community-governed, multi-party data space. Most data providers will also wish to act as data consumers, drawing data from the OAEBU IDS. However, data sharing and use is dependent on trust in the data space infrastructure and trust in every organizational participant connected to the data space to contribute or access OAEBU data.

Per the IDSA Rulebook:

*Establishing trust is fundamental to a data space. To create value from data, it needs to interact with other data and then support decision making. The different entities must trust each other - without trust, data will not be shared. **Data spaces can create context-specific trust where trust did not exist before or where it is difficult to establish -- for example between competitors.** (Source: IDSA Rulebook - https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/idsa-rulebook-v2/idsa-rulebook/3_functional_requirements, emphasis added)*

To sustain trust mechanisms and technical operations for data intermediation and aggregation, The [OA Book Usage Data Trust](#) is preparing to act as a governance authority that sustains and enforces the policies and participation rules for an OAEBU focused data space. Operationally, these secretariat functions would include facilitating community governance and advisory bodies, settling financial sustainability transactions, and facilitating standard legal agreements between data space participants.

Interoperability enabled by a web of interconnected data intermediation services

A sustainable data space must provide, directly or via partnership, both data intermediation and aggregation services in a neutral fashion as a trustee acting on behalf of the data space participants.²⁰ This intermediation serves to support relationships between the *Data Providers* and *Data Consumers* in a neutral, secure environment without bias. The IDSA has published certification and technical specifications for key data space intermediation roles.²¹ As defined in the 4th version of the Industry Data Space Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM 4.0)²², these roles include:

¹⁹ See https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/idsa-rulebook-v2/idsa-rulebook/2_guiding_principles and https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Infografik-English.pdf

²⁰ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/idsa-rulebook-v2/idsa-rulebook/2_guiding_principles

²¹ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/use/ids-components/>

²² https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0/blob/main/documentation/3_Layers_of_the_Reference_Architecture_Model/3_1_Business_Layer/3_1_1_Roles_in_the_IDS.md#business-roles-in-the-international-data-space

1. **Metadata Broker Service:** provides an index service of metadata shared by data connectors to facilitate link-based discovery of data sources. For the OAEBUDT, metadata broker(s) would index and/or share data specific to the OA Book Publishing and Discovery industries.
2. **IDS Clearing House:** provides for an accounting of data exchange and transformation (clearing) functions:
 - a. prior to data exchange, *e.g.* verifying usage policies, data access financial conditions, and logging transactions against a data sharing agreement;
 - b. during active data exchange, *e.g.* logging of sharing actions, tracing of data provenance, auditing, reporting and if applicable invoicing based on data transactions; and
 - c. after data exchange, *e.g.* investigation and enforcement of usage policy.
3. **App Store Provider:** securely hosts and provisions code for the data space (aka Apps) that transform, aggregate, or otherwise analyze OA Book Usage data according to transparent algorithms agreed upon by the data trust community
4. **Vocabulary Providers:** entities that manage ontologies, metadata, and persistent identifiers related to OA book usage, including vocabularies that relate to identifiers for books, chapters, DOIs, scholars, institutions, grants, and organizations. This category includes connecting to standard PIDS such as: ORCID, ROR, ONIX, ISBN.
5. **Identity Provider:** a Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) capable of asserting user and organizational identities with associated security and trust levels. For research and education, this could include global infrastructure networks such as the InCommon Federation.

The OAEBUDT effort is actively looking to identify existing platforms and services capable of fulfilling these five roles for an IDS for OA book usage data. To advance the development of a minimum-viable industrial data space for OA book usage, the OAEBUDT effort is planning to assess operational scholarly publishing service providers (Technical Readiness Levels 7-9) against the technical requirements specified in the IDS-RAM 4.0 and emerging certification specification documents for interconnected services.²³

Results of this analysis will be openly published and used to inform technical systems integration partnerships, research and development for an OAEBU IDS pilot from 2023-2025. Immediately upon completion, the analysis will inform: a) the development of the OAEBU IDS Technical Research and Development roadmap, b) systems integration to support an MVP pilot of usage data exchange between two cohorts of OAEBU data providers via IDS core service providers in the IDSA sandbox (2023-2025), and c) exploration into making the OAEBU IDS stack extensible to usage data for other scholarly outputs.

2. **IDS Governance Building Blocks: Policy and Practices to Steward Global Sovereign Data Exchange**
 Clear ethical norms and privacy and security guardrails are required to unlock data exchange for granular analytics. But, what are the “bright lines” and rules that are required to ensure that those who contribute data and those who rely on the data benefit from, trust in, and ultimately participate in a data space network? The global research community must support disparate cultural and policy approaches to data governance across national, regional, and stakeholder perspectives. Publishers may perceive their usage data as sensitive information, akin to print sales data. Platforms and services may perceive their raw usage data as sensitive insights into the strengths or weaknesses of particular offerings.

Evolving data regulations and controls – moving from fully open to as controlled as necessary

In the past few years, the perils of open data, big data harvesting, and unclear data processing has become clearer. Open data has been repurposed in unforeseen ways that negatively impact society. Open data can be repurposed for the common good but it can also enable the unethical, from AI model training leading to discriminatory practices to allowing the targeting of individuals for misinformation campaigns or worse.

²³ For more information about the evolution of Technical Readiness Levels in the US and Europe, see From NASA to EU: the evolution of the TRL scale in Public Sector Innovation. Mihály Héder. The Innovation Journal: The Public Sector Innovation Journal, Volume 22(2), 2017, article 3. https://web.archive.org/web/20171011071816/https://www.innovation.cc/discussion-papers/22_2_3_heder_nasa-to-eu-trl-scale.pdf

Responsive national and regional data regulations are emerging at different rates. Europe is advancing controlled data spaces to foster public-private data sharing according to industry-set terms; meanwhile, the US is piloting a National Secure Data Service for federal statistics while working to pass privacy protections equivalent to GDPR.

Security and risk management for IP Addresses (usage data) depends on geography

While the European Commission's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)²⁴ requires organizations to treat Internet Protocol (IP) addresses as sensitive personally identifiable data, the 'website cookie' tracking ecosystem is comparably laissez-fair. Multi-national data exchange must comply with the most restrictive regulatory regime; therefore, issues regarding the security, access, and use of raw IP addresses (i.e. personal data tied to specific book readership) must be addressed by the IDS if such data is to be exchanged for the greater good. Questions to consider will include: Does a data provider have the authority to share raw IP addresses, and if so, to whom and under what conditions? If not, could privacy-enhancing technologies be used to anonymize the information, and if so – which business cases would then be supported? A final consideration is whether the OAEBU data space must simply pass through raw OAEBU data only to those with contractual access agreements with data creators outside of the IDS.

Defining allowable raw data uses and acceptable algorithmic data processing for all participants in a data space allows a common experience and foundation for trust. The question for the global OA book stakeholder community is what principles should be implemented in the shared IDS infrastructure solution.

Developing principles through community consultation

To inform the administration and data governance practices of the OAEBUDT, an April 2023 workshop sponsored by the Mellon Foundation will gather OA book usage data producers and consumers to develop an initial set of principles to guide the secure exchange and downstream use of OAEBU data accessed through the data trust. Meeting outputs will then be shared broadly for feedback and iterative development prior to being finalized as an easy-to-read "data rulebook" and legal terms and conditions related to the processing and stewarding of usage data in the OAEBU IDS.

An initial small group of data providers and data consumers will gather to explore what's needed to ensure trust in an OAEBU data space. A month prior to their gathering, this group was presented with an initial set of questions to assess preliminary perspectives on what they perceived their organizations "must have" to share data or what would be "nice to have" or "unnecessary" in four domains. The goal of the exercise was to understand: a) what's important to those who rely on the usage data that would come out of the OAEBU-DT, and b) surface any response variance based on stakeholder type (e.g. library or publisher, or commercial or public) or region. Initial questions focused on assurances related to OAEBU data consistency, processing transparency, security, and risk reduction. As a follow-up exercise, participants will rate the importance of various mechanisms to assure trust in the data received. Results will inform discussions to produce draft principles for OA book stakeholder engagement with the OAEBUDT IDS.

Initial draft principles will undergo community consultation in summer 2023 to generate feedback from diverse global stakeholders. Expected venues for outreach and engagement will include feedback sessions led by OAEBUDT staff in-person at conferences and via online workshops, in addition to published online calls for consultation. A diverse task group of engaged knowledgeable stakeholder representatives will be invited to work with OAEBUDT staff to incorporate community feedback. Once refined, principles will be documented in an OAEBUDT rulebook for legal subject-matter experts to use as the basis for standard contractual clause (SCC) development for data trust participation and usage data sharing agreements.

²⁴ <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>

IDS sustainability and balanced stakeholder-based governance

While usage data policies for OAEBU data are being developed, an elected Board of Trustees for the OA Book Usage Data Trust is developing formal governance mechanisms, operational policies, and procedures to ensure diverse global participation and governance representation in the OAEBUDT IDS. In its second year of existence, the Board of Trustees shared their governance mechanisms at the April 2023 workshop for community consultation.

Governance policies and practices will be summarized in the OAEBUDT rulebook to provide transparency to data trust participants. Details will be documented in policy documents such as the OAEBU Data Trust Policies and Procedures and OAEBU Data Trust Governance By-laws.

3. IDS Technical Building Blocks: Scaffolding Data Quality, Trust, and Neutral Data Exchange

To automate the routing, processing, and delivery of usage data according to proscribed rules, an IDS requires a number of technical building blocks to manage identity authentication and access controls, routing, encryption, and anonymization. Provided by integrating data intermediation services, these technical building blocks provide the technical platform for the data space. The IDSA already offers a sandbox of open source solutions for developers to explore and test sample infrastructure that meets the IDSA certification requirements. IDS systems integrations firms are available to work with industry-specific data providers and data consumers to facilitate interconnections using the technical systems selected by a given IDS.

The OA Book Usage Data Trust aims to leverage existing infrastructures, avoiding the duplication of infrastructure unless absolutely necessary. Prior to developing the technical development roadmap for the OAEBUDT IDS, an IDS Component Technical Gap Analysis project will identify and assess existing scholarly infrastructures against the IDS requirements for the core IDS data intermediation. Gap analysis results will identify organizations and/or services in the OA book usage data ecosystem that could perform IDS related functional roles, noting additional development that would be needed to meet IDS certification and security requirements as described in the IDS technical Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM 4.0). Multiple platforms listed in the Open Access Books Usage Data Trust Environmental Scan²⁵ could be assessed, including: OpenAIRE, the EOSC Core, OA Switchboard, the Academic Observatory (backend to the Book Analytics Dashboard effort, CHORUS, the LENS, and technology implementation partners identified through the IDSA.

²⁵ Clarke, Michael. (2021). Open Access Books Usage Data Trust Environmental Scan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6415470>

Figure 4: Building blocks for data spaces from Nagel, Lars, and Douwe Lycklama. *Design Principles for Data Spaces*. International Data Spaces Association, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105744>. pg 42

Streamlining data curation, exchange, and aggregation

The value propositions for OAEBU Data Consumer participation in an OA Book Usage IDS revolve around simplifying the aggregation and normalization of usage data provided by multiple platforms. Beginning in April 2023, stakeholder consultations will define the APIs that must be included to achieve a minimum viable data space that is worth financial support. The initial set of APIs will be used to study the return on investment for data provider and data consumer participation in the IDS during two phases of pilots from 2024-2025. Initial APIs presented for consideration include:

- **Multi-platform usage API:** to access raw usage data from multiple platforms and services in accordance with existing business relationships that exist outside the OAEBUDT (e.g. platform/member, service/subscriber, publisher/library)
- **Aggregate Book Usage - COUNTER Compliant API:** COUNTER compliant metrics by book, aggregated across all participating OAEBUDT data providers
- **Aggregate Book Usage - Non- COUNTER Compliant API:** Non-COUNTER compliant metrics by book, aggregated across all participating OAEBUDT data providers who could not provide COUNTER-compliant data
- **Aggregate Chapter Usage - COUNTER Compliant API:** COUNTER compliant metrics by chapter, aggregated across all participating OAEBUDT data providers
- **Aggregate Chapter Usage - Non-COUNTER Compliant API:** Non-COUNTER compliant metrics by chapter, aggregated across all participating OAEBUDT data providers who could not provide COUNTER data
- **Disciplinary Benchmark Book Usage API:** Average usage benchmark metrics for all books in a given discipline, calculated across all participating OAEBUDT data providers providing COUNTER Compliant data.

This list is expected to evolve through consultation and minimum viable data space pilots conducted in 2024-2025.

Surfacing common goods that are otherwise not available

As the number of OAEBU Data Providers increases, it becomes possible for the IDS as a central neutral party to perform and publish community-agreed upon calculations across all data in transit. In line with the current OAEBU Data Trust Principles, algorithms could be openly published and applied to produce aggregate or benchmarking statistics for all participants to benefit from. The algorithms could be transparent much like IDS source code, even as the raw usage data supporting the calculations was made available under strictly controlled access and usage terms. Technically, an IDS for OA book publishing could centrally calculate and publish new data from across its corpus.

The allowable processing and use within a data space is determined by its industry. The question then becomes what ethical, privacy, and security guardrails are required for Data Providers to trust their data traversing the data space, for Data Consumers to trust the data they receive, and for Data Subjects (i.e. the readers, authors, and institutions related to the usage data) to not be harmed by the data space operations.

Conclusion

The importance of stewarding and providing access to comprehensive, high-quality scholarly usage data becomes paramount to retaining a culturally diverse and informed society. While some are concerned that data can be used to entrench discriminatory practices and foreclose options for a more equitable future, the OAEBU Data Trust's vision is to make data more widely and equitably shared, thereby shining a light on the dynamic state of book publishing access and impact to inform discussion, assessment and intervention around the diversity and impacts of OA book publishing.

Once operational, the OA Book Usage Data Trust will provide a cyberinfrastructure network in line with European Data Governance regulations, certified according to forthcoming European Industry Data Space trust and security standards to support international eBook usage data exchange among libraries, publishers, repositories, and the many platforms and services that wish to innovate with such metrics through data analytics and visualization services. By leveraging existing IDS frameworks, this project will provide scholarly publishing stakeholders with a means to migrate from data harvesting approaches and closed network data sharing via data lakes to sovereign ongoing data control with data exchange and aggregation enabled via community-governed data usage terms and blockchain technologies. This system aims to ensure that the personal and sensitive usage data being exchanged is shared in controlled ways that are as open and as transparent as possible yet as controlled as necessary to support trust, and ensure that participation and data use does not harm data creators or linked data subjects including readers, scholars, institutions, and libraries.

A critical prerequisite to ensuring trust when exchanging data among diverse, global data ecosystem stakeholders is a documented set of data stewardship practices and policies that make clear the processing, security, privacy, and use requirements and limitations for shared data. Work in 2023 will develop such rules for managing shared data and create common practices for data governance and exchange in service to the OA scholarly book community. Leveraging existing IDS rulebook examples and community consultations, the resulting OA Book Usage Data Trust rulebook will present a general-language description of how the OA Book Usage Data Trust will function to maintain trust for all involved. Standard contractual clauses for legal agreements and participation terms between parties will reflect such terms and be piloted in the first exchanges in the pilot IDS. Together such governance mechanisms will serve to create and maintain trust in the data space stewarded by the OA Book Usage Data Trust.

Bibliography

Automatic citation updates are disabled. To see the bibliography, click Refresh in the Zotero tab.

Acknowledgements

DRAFT